

SPEECH ETIQUETTES RELATED TO ADDRESSING AND METHODS TO TRANSLATE THEM FROM ENGLISH TO TURKMEN

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Abstract. *This article focusses on speech etiquette related to forms of addressing and explores methods of translating them from English into Turkmen. Language is considered not only as a means of communication but also as a reflection of cultural values and social relationships. The study highlights the differences between English and Turkmen addressing systems. The article is based on communicative, contrastive, and translation-oriented teaching methodologies. It applies a comparative and pragmatic approach to demonstrate that literal translation of speech etiquette often leads to cultural misunderstanding. Therefore, the use of functional equivalence is essential to preserve the communicative meaning of expressions. The findings show that effective translation and teaching of speech etiquette require not only linguistic knowledge but also intercultural competence. The article concludes that addressing forms should be taught and translated with careful consideration of cultural context and social norms.*

Keywords: *speech etiquette, forms of address, translation, English language, Turkmen language, communicative approach, intercultural competence.*

Introduction

The role of linguistics and literary studies is vital in describing a nation's glorious history, its happy life today and tomorrow, its contribution to world civilization, analyzing these through modern scientific-methodological ways, and sharing the nation's uniqueness with the world.

Language is considered a crucial tool for human communication and the exchange of ideas, and its importance in developing general culture is immense. Consequently, it is impossible to study the life or cultural level of any people without knowing their language [Gullaýew M., 1992, p. 5].

T. Tachmyradov explains in his work "Speech Etiquette of the Turkmen Language" that the term "speech etiquette" in a broad sense refers to exemplary texts of the written language and the potential capabilities of the entire language system. In a narrow sense, it refers to the practical implementation of language elements and possibilities in daily conversation. The author concludes that speech culture is a branch of linguistics that studies the development and refinement of our literary language—the tool of general culture—noting that speech culture is inseparably linked to the literary language and its norms [Tachmyradov T., 1986, pp. 21-33].

Speech etiquette encompasses all spheres of language use, including both spoken and written aspects (orthographic norms, punctuation rules, intonation, pauses, and stress). As noted, achieving the correct use of speech etiquette units according to Turkmen and English literary norms involves more than just adhering to rules in mass media or public speaking. It also involves preparing every individual who uses English

professionally or as a primary means of communication to structure their speech according to literary norms.

Language is not merely a tool for information exchange; it is a mirror of culture and social relations. The beginning of any conversation the etiquette of addressing defines the closeness and respect between the speakers. Because the English and Turkmen languages differ fundamentally in their historical and cultural roots, translating forms of address requires considering not just dictionary definitions, but pragmatic meaning as well.

Various types of words closely linked to a nation's culture, traditions, and customs are widely used in speech during daily interactions such as addressing someone, greeting, introducing oneself, saying goodbye, making requests, expressing gratitude, giving advice, offering blessings, or expressing condolences.

Main part

Speech etiquette is a product and tool of human cultural activity and a component of the culture of behavior and communication. According to scientists L.P. Stupin and K.S. Ignatyev (1980), speech etiquettes are the normative forms of speech used among members of a nation in their mutual relations. In other words, they are sets of standardized words used in specific social-communicative situations based on national-cultural and linguistic norms.

Speech etiquette is divided into several levels based on usage. While English addresses are often more direct and democratic, Turkmen addresses are based on family relations, age, and the respectful "Siz" (formal "you") form.

English Focus: Primarily on status and marital/social standing (Mr., Mrs., Ms., Dr.).

Turkmen Focus: Kinship terms (aga, uýa, daýza, jigi) are used even for strangers.

N.I. Formanovskaya and S.V. Shevtsova who have written many works on speech etiquette and are the authors of several monographs, divide speech etiquette into 15 groups in their work "Speech Etiquette Russian-English Correspondence" [Формановская Н.И., Шевцова, 1990, p.159]:

- 1) greetings;
- 2) addressing;
- 3) acquaintance;
- 4) invitation;
- 5) requests, advice;
- 6) agree or disagree with an invitation or request;
- 7) agree or disagree with interlocutor's opinion;
- 8) apologies;
- 9) complain;
- 10) express regret;
- 11) praise, approve;
- 12) disapprove;
- 13) congratulation, wish;
- 14) expressions of gratitude or condolences;
- 15) saying goodbye.

English address forms generally fall into three categories:

1. Formal addressing: *Sir, Madam, Your Honor, Excellency...*
2. Authority or professional titles: *Professor, Doctor, Officer...*

3. Affectionate /Family titles: *Mom, Dad, Honey, Buddy...*

In Turkmen, hundreds of words are used to address or draw attention, such as *eje, kaka, ata, ene, aga, inim, jigim, uýam, gelneje, ýeňňe, ýaşuly, dost, halypa* and dozens or hundreds of words. These include kinship terms used for specific individuals and nominative nouns used for addressing the public (*watandaşlar, kärdeşler, adamlar*).

Conclusion

Addressing words differ from other sentence members through intonation features like stress, tone, tempo, and pauses. While many works exist on this topic in various languages, it remains an under-researched area in Turkmen linguistics.

A.V. Veltistova defines an address as a word or phrase that carries intonational meaning, characterizes the speaker's intent (greeting, asking, commanding), and serves a communicative function by inviting a verbal response [10, p.28]. Similarly, A.F. Artyemova and E.O. Leonowich describe addressing as an inseparable part of daily life using names, pronouns, or adjectives.

Literal translation from English to Turkmen often leads to distorted meanings or cultural clashes. For example: "Sir" and "Madam": In a shop/service context, "Sir" might translate as "Müşderi" (Customer) or simply "Siz." In school, it means "Mugallym" (Teacher), and in the military, "Jenap".

Titles: Mr., Mrs., Miss, and Ms. often become respectful suffixes or specific titles added to the name in Turkmen (e.g., Mr. Brown becomes "Jenap Brawn" or "Brawn aga").

Kinship: In English, "Uncle" or "Aunt" is usually reserved for relatives, whereas in Turkmen, "daýy" or "daýza" is commonly used for older strangers.

Ultimately, translating speech etiquettes is about building a bridge between two cultures. A translator must consider the subtle nuances of speech culture to ensure the translation feels natural and is accepted by the reader.

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